

E-Learning and Job Performance of Academic Staff In Bayelsa State Owned Universities

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Abstract:- E-learning is a widely accepted concept in today ' s educational system . It ' s benefits are numerous . Enough empirical research on e-learning platforms for improving lecturer ' s performance as it affects Bayelsa State is not readily available . Hence this study bridges the information gap by making findings that are peculiar to the study population . This study adopted the explanatory crosssectional research survey design . The total population for the research work is 823 academic staff of the three state owned universities in Bayelsa State , Nigeria . Using Taro Yamane method for sample size calculation to determine the sample size , 269 questionnaires were distributed accordingly , following the proportion for distribution to the study population . A total of 230 questionnaires were retrieved . This is about 85 % retrieval success rate . Excel and Spss 25 . 0 software is then used to analyse data gotten from the field for univariate and bivariate analyses . Hypotheses were drawn to test the relationship between virtual classroom and lecturer effectiveness , creative teaching and time management . Findings show that lecturers are willing to adapt to change creatively to ensure that they effectively pass the required knowledge to their students.

Keywords:- E-learning , Virtual classroom , creative teaching , lecturer performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Advancement in technology all over the world has become evident in different industry today , and education is not left out . Students of tertiary education are in great pursuit of information ; they are keen to learn new things , ideas , technologies and new ways of acquiring information . This obviously occurs now that the world is fast turning into a global village . According to Hubackova (2015), new programs were created not only to teach , but also to allow the communication between the teacher and the student . This new system corresponded already with the today ' s one , but it got its name just in 1999 . The initial concept of e-learning was related with issues in contemporary essays primarily of a technical nature . This is the world of information and communication technology (ICT). According to Clover (2017), e-learning can also be referred to as Webbased learning or online learning . It essentially includes learning online through the courses that are offered on the net . Emails , live lectures , and videoconferencing are all made possible through the net . This enables all the participants to give their views on a particular topic and then discuss them further . They also

offer static pages like course materials that are printed for the benefit of all the participants (Clover , 2017). E-learning could shortly be defined as a webbased educational system on platform with Internet , Intranet or computer access . In this model , the lessons planned were simulations and software' s for students on polymers and metals (Sivalingam , et al . , 2018). Yucel (2016) through a study of E-learning Approach in Teacher Training viewed the concept of e-learning under two main subtitles as synchronized (where a group of students and an instructor actualize an online conference meeting in a computer environment) and asynchronized (where individuals actualize selftraining in computer environments). Students have access to the course contents whenever they want and communicate with their peers or teachers via communication tools such as email and forums . In order for the distance learning system to succeed in e(learning , the program should be planned as both synchronized and asynchronized Yucel , 2016). Various types of collaborators ranging from professional webbased designing firms , content writers and design formulators have begun to act together to create webbased E-learning programs designed to enhance learning through the recognition of various different types of student needs (Franklin and Nahari 2018). Franklin and Nahari in their research work portrayed that having the necessary resources for E-learning alone would not only directly influence the improved job performance of academic staff but would also positively affect the performance of students . They explained that students have different learning capabilities and as such overall best result from e-learning would be achieved if individual differences are put into consideration. E-learning as discussed in the background of study shows that it' s a widely accepted concept for the educational system. However, in Bayelsa State most tertiary. Institutions do not make use of it in their academic programs and processes. The question here is; Why are schools not making use of this technology? Is it as a result of insufficient funds? Could be because of inadequate knowledge of the concept of e-learning? Is it because of lack of facility? If schools are to adopt the e-learning methods of reaching , based on the peculiarity of the current environment and other factors to be considered, which form of e-learning platform would be best fit and can produce maximum result when matched with job performance of academic staffs? It can be identified that e-learning is a widely accepted concept for the educational system. However, in Bayelsa State most tertiary institutions have not properly utilized it in their academic programs and processes.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The aim of this study is to examine the correlation between E-learning and job performance of academic staff in Bayelsa State owned universities.

The specific objectives of this study will include the following: (1) To examine the correlation between virtual class room and lecturer effectiveness of academic staff in Bayelsa State owned universities. (2) To determine the relationship between virtual classroom and creative teaching practices of academic staff in Bayelsa State owned universities. (3) To examine how virtual classroom will lead to efficient time management of academic staff in Bayelsa State owned universities .

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

E-learning can best be defined as the science of learning without using paper printed instructional material (Goyal , 2012). It is the use of computer devices , mobile devices , internet connectivity , and application platforms that are programmed with capability to deliver information for education and training . E-learning is not a new phenomenon in promoting education in some parts of the world . Presently , some institutions in Nigeria are using it to promote distance education (DE) and lifelong learning (Ajadi , et al . , 2018). The development of e-learning in Nigeria could be traced back to the development of telecommunication which began in 1886 when cable connections was established by the colonial masters between Lagos and the colonial office in London to transmit information and receive feedback . By 1893 , all government offices in Lagos were provided with telephone service for easy communication , feedback and easy access and later all other parts of the country were provided with telephone services (Ajadi , et al . , ibid). In the late eighties and nineties of the last century , the first form of electronic education ; computer based training (CBT) was born (Hubackova , 2015). A study conducted by Alkhalaf , et al . (2012), shows positive attitudes towards E-learning systems in higher education , helping faculty members to improve their job performance , and educational organizations to provide better and new products and services to users . E-learning Systems are a technological development that have reformed and restructured the delivery and interaction of students and teachers with course materials and related resources (Alkhalaf , et al . , 2012). A study conducted by Sivalingam et al , (2018) on E-learning approach in Teacher Education analyzed a new model approach to E-learning and drew a conclusion that the experiments in the new model were appropriate to teacher training programs and could successfully be administered to large groups . It is worthy of note that E-learning tools and processes are not just confined to lecturer and student as they can be used even at job place trainings , conferences , etc . (Khan , 2019). E-learning with its egalitarian environment of open access provides greater opportunities for learners , particularly adult learners . Learnercentered educational opportunities through the use of virtual classrooms could satisfy learners ' need for convenient offerings and at the same time optimize the use of online learning (Subramaniam & Kandasamy 2011). Subramaniam and Kandasamy (2011)

also defined Virtual classroom as an online learning environment that contains all course materials . Virtual classroom has been described by Anekwe (2017) as a webbased environment that allows an individual to participate in live training events without traveling to any other place . This means that an individual can sit in the comfort of any given environment and listen / see lectures online . The individual can participate in the lab exercises , ask questions and effectively interact with an instructor as if the action is taking place in a traditional classroom environment but it is done with the convenience of technological gadgets as desktop that have internet and phone connections . Employers in different industries have consistently sourced for ways to get the best out of an employee as it has always been a major challenge an employer face in today ' s competitive environment . These , can be linked to the constantly changing work environment where new methods , skills and policies are necessary to be introduced to the employees . According to Inuwa , Mashi and Salisu (2017), an employee is most dynamic and unpredictable aspect of business resources . It has therefore become imperative for organizations to realize the significance of an employee and also the device strategic means through which an employee can be influenced in order to develop positive job attitudes that can lead to higher performance . Chuan and Heng (2012) in their research work on lecturer effectiveness , investigated lecturers ' teaching effectiveness using students ' end of the semester ' s evaluation . Findings from their work disclosed areas of knowledge and skills that lecturers should consider for further enhancement of their teaching effectiveness and if the evaluated results are seriously taken into consideration , it can lead to overall quality improvement of the lecturer ' s teaching effectiveness . In a similar study of lecturer effectiveness , undergraduate accounting students in University of Malaysia Sabah (UMS) was used as a case study to evaluate student perception on teaching methods and lecturer characteristics that they considered as effective in their learning process . Findings in the research indicate that attitude of the lecturers play an important role in delivering an effective teaching . Lecturers who have the most positive attitude in their teaching and learning process considered as the main element in giving the students the positive impact to what they are learning in class (Mohidin et al . 2019). Lecturer characteristics such as ; Knowledge / Experetise , Attitude , Personality plays an important role in determining the effective teaching especially in accounting subjects (Mohidin et al . ibid).

According to Woolfitt (2015), “ Video is permeating our educational institutions , transforming the way we teach , learn , study , communicate , and work . Harnessing the power of video to achieve improved outcomes for example , a better grade in exams / assignments or more effective knowledge transfer is becoming an essential skill . A key pillar in the drive towards improved digital literacy , video brings considerable benefits to educational institutions : streamlined admissions , increased retention , and improved learning outcomes ”. Since the 1970s , cognitive psychological perspectives have dominated pedagogical frameworks and models for designing technologymediated teaching and learning environments (Hill , Song and West , 2019).

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the explanatory cross-sectional research survey design . This research design is a form of research design that involves the generation of data from a portion of a large population with the use of questionnaire and using the data gotten to test hypothesis . It was chosen for this research work because ; the population under study is tertiary institution of Bayelsa State , which is quite a large population . Another reason is a portion of the entire population is what we need to test the hypothesis for e-learning platforms and job performance of academic staff . The presentation and analysis of data / results was done using Excel and Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) Version 25 . 0 . A structured questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection . Cronbach Alpha coefficient below 0 . 70 will be considered to be indicative of a weak or low reliability while 0 . 70 and above

is considered to be indicative of an acceptable level of reliability . The table below shows the level of reliability of the instrument used in this study .

➤ *Sample / Sampling Techniques*

The total population for the research work is 823 academic staff of the three state owned universities in Bayelsa State . Taro Yamane method for sample size calculation is used to calculate the sample size of the study .

Taro Yamane formula

$$n = N / (1 + N (e)^2$$

n = samplesize

N = study population

e = Marginerror = 0 . 05

N = 823

$$n = 269 . 17 = 269$$

Sample size is 269

S/N	Institution	Academic staff	Percentage	Number of Unit allocated
1	Bayelsa Medical University, Yenagoa. Bayelsa State. (BMU)	65	8%	21
2	Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Amassoma, Bayelsa State. (NDU)	622	75%	203
3	University of Africa, Toru-orua, Bayelsa State. (UAT)	125	17%	45
Total		823	100%	269

Table 1:- Population proportion

A total of 269 questionnaires were distributed. At the point of analysis 230 questionnaires were successfully retrieved.

This shows the cronbach’s alpha is .80. This means that the Cronbach Alpha analysis for this research presents an acceptable level of reliability.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.80	23

Table 2:- Reliability Statistics

➤ *Presentation and Analysis*

For the purpose of carrying out this survey research work, 269 questionnaires were distributed accordingly, following the proportion for distribution to the study population. A total of 230 questionnaires were retrieved. This is about 85% retrieval success. Excel and Spss 25.0 software is then used to analyse data gotten from the field for univariate and bivariate analyses.

Question	Total	Strongly Agree(%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Total (%)
Q1	230	50%	47%	2%	2%	0%	100%
Q 2	230	19%	36%	0%	45%	0%	100%
Q 3	230	20%	46%	9%	27%	0%	100%
Q 4	230	17%	33%	4%	45%	0%	100%
Q 5	230	20%	45%	0%	36%	0%	100%
Q 6	230	21%	54%	4%	21%	0%	100%
Q 7	230	8%	31%	4%	57%	0%	100%
Q 8	230	14%	30%	13%	34%	11%	100%
Q 9	230	45%	44%	3%	9%	0%	100%
Q 10	230	22%	30%	0%	48%	0%	100%
Q 11	230	48%	48%	0%	5%	0%	100%
Q 12	230	9%	38%	0%	54%	0%	100%
Q 13	230	0%	86%	8%	6%	0%	100%
Q 14	230	37%	19%	19%	18%	8%	100%

Q 15	230	6%	25%	9%	40%	20%	100%
Q 16	230	0%	34%	4%	39%	23%	100%
Q 17	230	19%	76%	6%	0%	0%	100%
Q 18	230	0%	58%	14%	12%	16%	100%
Q 19	230	0%	11%	1%	40%	49%	100%
Q 20	230	19%	24%	0%	45%	11%	100%
Q 21	230	0%	27%	6%	31%	37%	100%
Q 22	230	4%	50%	10%	36%	0%	100%
Q 23	230	34%	52%	0%	14%	0%	100%

Table 3:- Analysis of Questionnaire Items

The table above illustrate percentages of responds gotten from respondents as to the degree of their acceptance to the

questions asked in the questionnaire. Their response to questions ranged from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

➤ Demographic Analysis

Name of Institution	Questionnaires Administered	Questionnaires Retrieved	Percentage of Questionnaires Retrieved	Percentage of Shortage
BMU	21	21	8%	0%
NDU	203	171	75%	2.5%
UAT	45	38	17%	11.5%
Total	269	230	100%	14%

Table 4:- Percentage Rating of Respondents

➤ Respondent Analysis

STAFF DESIGNATION	NO. RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE	GENDER	
			MALE	FEMALE
Senior Lecturer	21	9%	15	6
Lecturer 1	45	20%	35	10
Lecturer 2	58	25%	28	30
Assistant Lecturer	73	32%	48	25
Graduate Assistant	33	14%	26	7
Total	230	100%	152	78

Table 5 :- Respondent Analysis

A total no. of 230 staff participated in the research work as respondents out of this number 152 are men and 72 are women. The highest number of participants from the percentage ratings is Assistant lecturers while the lowest participant gotten based on designation are senior lecturers.

Ho1: There is no significant correlation between virtual class room and lecturer effectiveness of academic staff in Bayelsa State owned Universities.

Correlations				
			Virtual Classroom	Lecturer Effectiveness
Spearman's rho	Virtual Classroom	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.001
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.994
		N	299	299
	JobPerformance	Correlation Coefficient	-.001	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.994	.
		N	229	230

Table 6:- Correlations between virtual Classroom and lecturer effectiveness

From the table, the P value of -0.001 is less than the standard alpha value of 0.05 ($p < \alpha$) therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant relationship between virtual classroom and lecturer effectiveness of academic staff in Bayelsa State owned universities.

Ho2: There is no significant correlation between virtual classroom and creative teaching practice of academic staff in Bayelsa State owned Universities.

CORRELATIONS		Virtual Classroom	Creative Teaching
Spearman's rho	Virtual Classroom	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.
		N	299
	Creative Teaching	Correlation Coefficient	-.072
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.315
		N	229

Table 7:- Correlation between virtual classroom and creative teaching

There was a significant negative correlation between virtual classroom and creative teaching practices of academic staff. $r_s(199) = -0.07, p < 0.05$.

Ho3: There is no significant correlation between virtual classroom and efficient time management of academic staff in Bayelsa State owned Universities.

Correlations			
		Virtual Classroom	Efficient Time Management
Spearman's rho	Virtual Classroom	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.
		N	229
	Efficient Time Management	Correlation Coefficient	-.018
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.804
		N	229

Table 8 :- Correlation between virtual classroom and efficient time management

There is a significant negative correlation between virtual classroom and efficient time management of academic staff. $r_s(229) = 0.02, p < 0.05$. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant correlation between virtual classroom and efficient time management of academic staff of Bayelsa State owned Universities.

V. CONCLUSION

Sife, Lwoga, & Sanga (2007) viewed that developing countries are yet to have developed a strong ICT that would match up with latest trends. This is as a result of underlying socioeconomic and technological factors that are inherent in these regions. Advancement in information technology is a continuous process. Software developers are constantly looking into the future and working round the clock to develop userfriendly and more sophisticated applications using latest technology available. The educational sector needs to follow this global trend in the delivery of study content and class participation to ensure their effectiveness and relevance in their very unique field they operate in. Hence, adopting new process of delivering lectures where distance would not be a barrier is very vital especially in this COVID19 era. In the course of this study, it was found that, lecturers believe that the use of electronic platforms for learning alongside traditional classrooms of meeting students physically is necessary. Findings also show that lecturers are

willing to adapt to change creatively to ensure that they adequately pass the required knowledge to their students. Further research could be geared towards government intervention strategies to strengthen distant learning and also tackling distractions and limitations that are associated to e-learning activities. Government can do more in their approach to funding and encouraging e-learning activities haven seen the importance and impact it will have on the performance of academic staff.

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